

ACCOUNTING FOR MANUFACTURABILITY CONSTRAINTS IN THE OPTIMISATION OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

V. Madhavan^{1*}, P. Martiny¹

¹ Composite Structures and Processes, Cenaero, Gosselies, Belgium

* Corresponding author (vinay.madhavan@cenaero.be)

Keywords: *manufacturability, composite design, finite elements, optimisation, blending*

1 Introduction

This paper presents a methodology to optimise a fibre reinforced composite component with respect to weight, aeronautical design rules and manufacturing constraints. One of the primary advantages of fibre reinforced composites in structural applications is the ability to tailor the strength and stiffness of the component at various locations to suit the encountered loading conditions. In the design process of tailoring laminates, certain rules need to be followed to ensure better quality parts and lower costs in terms of manufacturing. For the aeronautics industry, the critical rules have been listed in Table 1 [1].

In addition to these rules, it is encouraged that designers try to maintain as much ply continuity (the number of plies that can be continuously laid across multiple zones also known as ‘blending’) in the structure as possible since this would reduce manufacturing costs and prevent stress discontinuities between adjacent panels. However, as discussed in [2], ply continuity constraints almost always result in weight penalties in-turn increasing the complexity of this type of optimisation. Due to previously mentioned reasons, this cannot be neglected to obtain a realistic composite structure. The blending approach has been used extensively in previous research to optimise composite structures. The blending method is mostly used in conjunction with some form of ply shuffling techniques which range from explicit definition of ply orientations to parameters representing groups of plies to be arranged in a laminate [3,4]. Usually these techniques tend to result in a large number of optimisation parameters producing a large solution space which needs to be sampled.

The approach followed in this paper utilises a bi-level optimisation where the global level

optimisation makes use of the Minamo optimisation software to minimise the mass while taking into account the structural response of the structure and the manufacturability of the structure. The local level optimisation (purely analytical) is used to generate the optimum stacking sequences for all zones from the input parameters. The structure of the bi-level optimisation has been illustrated in Fig. 1.

The current methodology aims to limit the number of parameters/design variables (DV) per laminate to one at the global level. This single DV per laminate is generated by the global level optimisation and transferred to the local level optimisation where the optimum stacking sequence for each domain is determined. The DVs generated by the global level optimisation are the total number of plies per laminate. Using this information along with the material data and the inter-zone connectivities, the optimum combination of stacking sequences for the whole structure is obtained in the local level optimisation. The selection process at the local level involves a combination of multiple sorting criteria in a step-by-step elimination process. This results in stacking sequences which are blended, design rules compliant and manufacturing rules compliant. The optimum stacking sequences are then used to generate a global finite element model (GFEM) of the structure and test for laminate failure (maximum strain) and buckling failure. The GFEM utilises the NASTRAN finite element code.

The advantage of this technique is the reduced solution space resulting directly from the single DV per laminate at the global level optimisation. A reduced solution space means a reduced number of function calls to the finite element solver which typically is the most computationally expensive part of an optimisation loop (generation).

The purpose of this optimisation chain is to be able to efficiently optimise the structural response of

large continuous structures with varying requirements for strength and stiffness. The benchmark case-study chosen to demonstrate the abilities of this optimisation chain was the optimisation of composite skin panels on a section of an aircraft. The GFEM for the structure was provided by Bombardier Aerospace and can be seen in Fig. 2.

2 Stacking sequence generation

A stacking sequence generation tool was developed in the programming language PYTHON to generate a list of stacking sequences for various connected / non-connected zones in a component / structure. This tool has been referred to as the local level optimisation in the previous section. The code tries to ensure that both design and manufacturing rules (as discussed in [1]) are respected. In the final step, the optimum stacking sequences are chosen based on the local buckling strength. The overall structure of the stacking sequence generation tool has been illustrated in the flowchart in Fig. 3. It may be seen that the process can be broken down into several sub-processes. These sub-processes are described in the following sections.

2.1 Handling of parameters and preliminary sorting

The input parameters for the stacking sequence generator tool are subdivided into two categories, design variables and design constants. The design variables are the total number of plies per zone. For example, consider a plate with 4 zones, P_1 , P_2 , P_3 and P_4 , the input parameters are n_1 to n_4 where n_i is the number of plies in the laminate P_i . The design constants are the material properties of the lamina (single layer), the compliance required for the design and manufacturing rules and the connectivity between zones. Taking the same case-study of a plate with 4 zones, the connectivity would be defined by listing all the zones which each domain is a neighbour of. Let us assume that the connectivities are as follows (which corresponds to the subdivision of the base plate in a 2x2 array of laminates):

- $P_1 - [P_2, P_3]$
- $P_2 - [P_1, P_4]$
- $P_3 - [P_1, P_4]$
- $P_4 - [P_2, P_3]$

At this stage a check is performed to ensure that the difference in total number of plies between neighbouring laminates does not exceed 4 plies. If one connection exceeds that limit, the stacking sequence generator tool exits with a failed status. This does not ensure that manufacturing rule 10 (max. ply drops = 4) is respected but it is used as a go/no-go check at this stage. In fact, note that at this stage ply orientations are not yet defined.

The next step in the generation chain is determining all feasible combinations of number of plies per orientation for each laminate (zone). It is to be noted that the result from this sub-section of the code is individual laminate based and provides all suitable options of number of plies per orientation per laminate. The feasibility of the laminate is determined by the design rules Rule 1 to Rule 3 since these rules do not depend on the actual stacking sequence of the laminate. Since the stacking sequences are considered to be symmetric and balanced, only half the total number of plies is considered in the analysis. Design rule 5 states that there can be a maximum of 1 ply between a +45 ply and a -45 ply. Nevertheless, the current version of the code restricts the ± 45 plies to lie adjacent to each other and grouped together as a single ply. This is done to reduce the total number of combinations.

2.2 Global continuity table and shared layer blending

The preliminary sorting analysis discussed in the previous section generated multiple possibilities of number of plies per orientation for each laminate. The global continuity analysis utilises these results to generate all possible instances of permutations for the structure, assesses their level of global ply continuity and stores them in a table. For example, if we consider the plate with 4 zones again, and P_i has n_{P_i} solutions, then the total number of instances in the Global continuity table will be $n_{P_1} * n_{P_2} * n_{P_3} * n_{P_4}$. Each of these instances is then evaluated for global continuity. This is done by determining the number of plies in the structure which can be continuously laid out across the entire structure and divided by the number of plies in the thickest laminate. This does not have any relation to the connectivity between neighbouring zones. It is purely related to increasing the feasibility of manufacturing. Typically this value in industry is around 70% to 80% [2] (100% ply continuity indicates that all laminates in the structure

are identical). The global continuity is then used to filter out instances which do not meet the predefined minimum global continuity (set to 70% in the environment variables of the stacking sequence generator tool). If none of the instances meet the predefined minimum global continuity, the stacking sequence generator exits with a failed status. The results from the global continuity analysis are then further processed by performing the shared layer blending analysis.

Unlike the global ply continuity assessment, the shared layer blending analysis accounts directly for the connectivity between neighbouring laminates. The shared layer blending approach followed in this research is similar to the work done by [4] where a step by step iteration through the laminates of the structure is performed to identify shared layers globally (full structure) and locally (between connected laminates). To illustrate the methodology followed, consider the 4 zone case-study defined in previous sections. Let us assume that P_1 consists of 6 0° plies, 4 90° plies and 8 $\pm 45^\circ$ plies which is represented as (6,4,8). Similarly, P_2 (6,6,8), P_3 (4,8,6) and P_4 (8,4,6). The first step is similar to the global ply continuity analysis where the number of shared ply orientations across the structure are identified. So in the example above, the first shared layer will have the configuration (4,4,6) and the remaining plies in laminates P_1 to P_4 are respectively (2,0,2), (2,2,2), (0,4,0) and (4,0,0). The second step in the analysis identifies the connected laminates and extracts the common orientations (from the remaining plies) for all the connections to establish local continuity between the connections. From the previous sections we know that the connections and their common orientations are as follows (removing duplicate connections):

- $P_1 - P_2$ (2,0,2)
- $P_1 - P_3$ (0,0,0)
- $P_2 - P_4$ (2,0,0)
- $P_3 - P_4$ (0,0,0)

By performing this analysis we find that the remaining plies for laminates P_1 to P_4 are now respectively (0,0,0), (0,2,0), (0,4,0) and (2,0,0).

This analysis is performed for each instance in the global ply continuity table and a new table is generated containing the three levels of shared layers for each instance (1. Plies shared globally across the

structure, 2. Plies shared between connections, 3. Remaining un-shared plies).

To improve the efficiency of the computation, the symmetric-balanced condition is made use of here. So considering P_1 which is a 18 ply laminate defined as (6,4,8), only half the stack is used in the shared layer assessment making it (3,2,4). Additionally, design rule 7 dictates that the outer plies should be $\pm 45^\circ$, so these two plies are removed from each laminate before the analysis, making P_1 (3,2,2). It is to be noted that the same solution is reached for the shared layer analysis but more efficiently. Table 2 illustrates the shared layer blending process. Shared layer 1, Shared layer 2 and Remaining (final) are referred to as the three shared layers of a single laminate. The next step involves obtaining all the permutations of stacking sequences for each laminate. This is done in four steps.

1. Determine all permutations of stacking sequences for the first shared layer (common to all laminates)
2. Determine all the permutations of stacking sequences for the second shared layer (individual to each laminate)
3. Determine all the permutations of stacking sequences for the remaining layers (individual to each laminate)
4. Determine all the permutations of the full stacking sequence of each laminate based on permutations of the first 3 steps.

To illustrate these three steps we return to the 4 zone case-study. Consider P_1 for which we found the three shared layers to be (2,2,1), (1,0,1) and (0,0,0). In step one we consider the first shared layer which has the un-ordered orientations (0° , 0° , 90° , 90° , 45°). This results in a total number of permutations equal to 120 (factorial 5) and by removing duplicate permutations (due to multiple occurrences of the same orientation angle) we end up with 30 permutations for the first shared layer (common to all 4 laminates). Similarly, in steps 2 and 3 we compute the permutations for the two remaining layers resulting in 2 and 0 permutations respectively (represented as [30,2,0]). The computation is repeated for the 3 other laminates resulting in:

- P_1 - [30,2,0]
- P_2 - [30,2,1]
- P_3 - [30,0,1]
- P_4 - [30,1,1]

In step 4 the permutations between the three layers for each laminate is computed to determine all the possible stacking sequences. In the case of P_1 this results in 60 (per_1) permutations. Similarly, for P_2 to P_4 we can compute the number of permutations to be 60 (per_2), 30 (per_3) and 30 (per_4) respectively. Then all permutations between the permutations of P_1 to P_4 are computed and stored in the Global Stacking Sequence Table (GSST). Each of the permutations in the GSST is a potential optimum case of stacking sequences for all the laminates. The total number of cases in the GSST for the case-study amounts to 3.24 million. This figure includes a large number of non-feasible solutions since (i) the stacking sequence for the first shared layer is chosen independently for each laminate, and, (ii) the stacking sequence for each second shared layer is chosen independently for the different laminates they are shared across. These are filtered out at a later stage by the manufacturing rules.

The total number of cases (n_{GSST}) can be calculated using Equation 1.

$$n_{GSST} = per_1 * per_2 * per_3 * per_4 \quad (1)$$

All permutations are computed using standard permutations methods which are built into the PYTHON programming language [5]. Please note that the example stated above is a highly simplified case (for illustration purposes) which does not show the complexity of computation when more than 2 zones have shared layers at the second step.

2.3 Filtering by manufacturing and design rules assessment

In the generation of the stacking sequences over the last 3 phases design rules 1, 2, 3, 5, and 7 were addressed and enforced to be compliant at 100%. At this stage, rules 4 and 6 are used to filter out any unwanted cases from the n_{GSST} cases in the GSST. These two rules do not have to be compliant at 100% and their compliance level can be set by the user. Rule 4 states that a maximum of three plies of the same orientation can be grouped together and Rule 6 states that a maximum angle of 45° can exist between a ply and a group of plies with the same orientation. These two rules are tested for all laminates case by case. If in an individual case, one or more laminates fail to match either criterion with the user-defined percentage of compliance, the entire case is dropped from the GSST. The assessment of

design rules is done on the full stacking sequence and not on the half stack.

The updated GSST from the design rules assessment (Rules 1 to 7 in Table 1) is then further filtered by the assessment of manufacturing rules (Rules 8 to 12 in Table 1). In this assessment, laminates from neighbouring zones are analysed for rules 8 and 10. Rule 11 is imposed at 100% due to the fact that the ±45° plies were grouped together during the stacking sequence generation. Rule 12 is also imposed due to the methodology used in the shared layer assessment. This type of blending is commonly called inward blending [6] and results in 100% compliance of rule 12. Rule 9 which states that outer plies should be continuous, is also indirectly imposed to 100% due to rule 7 which states that the outer plies should be ±45°. To determine the compliance of rule 8, the equivalent material properties of each laminate needs to be determined and the difference in Poisson's ratio computed between neighbouring laminates. This is done using Classical Laminate Theory. The following steps are performed individually for each laminate [1].

Step 1: Computation of the stiffness matrix of a single ply $[Q]$:

$$[Q] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{21}E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{12}E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where, $E_{11}, E_{22}, \nu_{12}, \nu_{21}$ and G_{12} are material constants.

Step 2: Computation of transformed stiffness matrices ($[\bar{Q}]$) for each ply of orientation θ $[0^\circ, 90^\circ, \pm 45^\circ]$:

$$[\bar{Q}]_\theta = [T]_\theta^{-1} [Q] [T]_\theta^{-T} \quad (3)$$

$$[T]_\theta = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2\theta & \sin^2\theta & 2\sin\theta\cos\theta \\ \sin^2\theta & \cos^2\theta & -2\sin\theta\cos\theta \\ -\sin\theta\cos\theta & \sin\theta\cos\theta & \cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Step 3: Computation of the bending $[A]$ and membrane $[D]$ stiffness matrices of the laminate:

$$A_{i,j} = \sum_{k=1}^N (\bar{Q}_{\theta,i,j})_k (Z_k - Z_{k-1}) \quad (5)$$

$$D_{i,j} = 1/3 \sum_{k=1}^N (\bar{Q}_{\theta,i,j})_k (Z_k^3 - Z_{k-1}^3) \quad (6)$$

Where N denotes the total number of plies in the laminate, $Z = 1, 2, \dots, N$ represents the position in the laminate and $i, j = 1, 2, 6$

Step 4: Computation of membrane and bending Poisson's ratios:

(a) Membrane:

$$v_{xy} = -\frac{a_{12}}{a_{11}}; v_{yx} = -\frac{a_{12}}{a_{22}} \quad (7)$$

(b) Bending:

$$v_{xy} = -\frac{d_{12}}{d_{11}}; v_{yx} = -\frac{d_{12}}{d_{22}} \quad (8)$$

Where $[a]$ and $[d]$ are the inverse of the $[A]$ and $[D]$ matrices respectively. The magnitude of the difference between the Poisson's ratios for the two laminates is computed and the maximum difference is checked against the reference maximum difference (0.15).

Rule 10 is computed using a sequential block matching algorithm as documented in [5] to determine the number of real ply drops between neighbouring zones. The algorithm scans through the two sequences and identifies common blocks of orientations. The total number of non-matched orientations gives the number of ply drops. The allowable number of ply drops is set by the user.

As in the case of the design rules assessment, if any of the connections do not meet the criteria (established by the user), the case is dropped from the GSST. This specific part of the code is run multi-threaded.

2.4 Computation of critical buckling factors

For the optimisation discussed in this paper, the critical failure mode of the structure is buckling. For this reason, the buckling factors were used to perform the final filtering of the cases as discussed in the previous sections. The same methodology may be used with a failure index (using classical laminate theory) for a more standard structural optimisation. The finite element model used in the current study uses a mesh density for global sizing and optimisation (large elements – 1 element per bay). It is not possible to numerically (FE) extract eigenvalue solutions from these mesh sizes so analytical methods for computing the critical buckling loads had to be implemented. The aim was to compute the local buckling factors (at the bay by bay level of the FE model) using buckling equations for flat plates to determine the uniaxial buckling factor, the biaxial buckling factor, the shear buckling factor and the combined shear and uniaxial buckling factors. The different possible types of loading on

each bay have been illustrated in Fig. 4. The equations used to compute the critical buckling factors are based in simply supported boundary conditions and have been listed below:

(a) Uniaxial loading:

This type of loading may be either in the 0° direction (longitudinal) or in the 90° direction (transverse). Equation 9 (longitudinal loading on long edge), Equation 10 (longitudinal loading on short edge) and Equation 11 (transverse loading) demonstrate the methodology used to compute the buckling factors [7]. $D_{m,n}$ represents the terms in the $[D]$ matrix as computed in the previous section. While i and j are index values that help identify the minimum eigenvalue. The values of i and j are varied from 1 to 6. In the case of uniaxial loading, the code checks the type of uniaxial load that is applied on the structure and then the appropriate equation is used.

$$N_x \cdot (\lambda_{cr})_{ij} = \pi^2 \left[D_{11} \left(\frac{i}{L_x} \right)^2 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \left(\frac{j}{L_y} \right)^2 + D_{22} \left(\frac{L_x}{i} \right)^2 \left(\frac{j}{L_y} \right)^4 \right] \quad (9)$$

$$N_x \lambda_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_y^2} \left[2\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \right] \quad (10)$$

$$N_y \cdot (\lambda_{cr})_{ij} = \pi^2 \left[D_{11} (i/L_x)^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) (i/L_x)^2 * (j/L_y)^2 + D_{22} (j/L_y)^4 \right] / (j/L_y)^2 \quad (11)$$

(b) Biaxial loading:

This buckling case takes into account the axial loading in the two in-plane material directions (longitudinal and transverse). Equation 12 demonstrates the methodology used to compute the buckling factor [7]. This condition is only computed if the two loads could potentially result in buckling of the structure (i.e. if N_x and N_y are tensile, there would be no combined buckling, but if either N_x or N_y is compressive, buckling may occur).

$$N_x \cdot (\lambda_{cr})_{ij} = \pi^2 \left[D_{11} (i/L_x)^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) (i/L_x)^2 * (j/L_y)^2 + D_{22} (j/L_y)^4 \right] / \left((i/L_x)^2 + (j/L_y)^2 / AR \right) \quad (12)$$

where,

$$AR = N_x / N_y \quad (13)$$

(c) Shear loading:

Equation 14 demonstrates the methodology used to compute the buckling factor [7]. This condition is only computed if a shear load is present.

$$N_{xy}\lambda_{cr} = \begin{cases} \frac{4\beta}{L_y^2} \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}^3} & 0 \leq k \leq 1 \\ \frac{4\beta}{L_y^2} \sqrt{D_{22}(D_{12} + 2D_{66})} & 1 < k \leq \infty \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where,

$$k = (2D_{66} + D_{12})/\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} \quad (15)$$

$$\beta = \begin{cases} 8.125 + 5.045k & 0 \leq k \leq 1 \\ 11.71 + \frac{1.46}{k^2} & 1 < k \leq \infty \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

(d) Combined shear and longitudinal loading:

Equation 17 demonstrates the methodology used to compute the buckling factors from combined loading [8]. This condition is only computed if the two loads could potentially result in buckling of the structure.

$$N_x\lambda_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{L_x^2 \left(2 - \frac{8192L_x^2k^2}{81L_y^2\pi^4} \right)} \times \left(D_{11} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{L_x^2}{L_y^2} + D_{22} \frac{L_x^4}{L_y^4} \right) \times \left[5 \pm \sqrt{9 + \frac{65536L_x^2k^2}{81\pi^4L_y^2}} \right] \quad (17)$$

where,

$$N_{xy} = kN_x \quad (18)$$

In order to compute the critical buckling factor λ_{cr} for each type of buckling, the element dimensions and the forces on the bay (or element) were required. A single finite element simulation is run in NASTRAN (see section 3 for details about the finite element model) with the current laminate thicknesses (from the global level optimisation) and quasi-isotropic material properties to determine the internal loads on each bay. For a given thickness, a quasi-isotropic stacking sequence represents the minimum performance that can be expected from a laminate. Therefore the corresponding critical buckling factors $\lambda_{cr,ref}$ are a good reference point for an optimisation study. Since $\lambda_{cr,ref}$ is a normalised factor (to the reference applied load from the quasi-isotropic analysis), it is possible to use it to estimate the most critical region/element in the

structure. Please note that this value of $\lambda_{cr,ref}$ is relative to the quasi-isotropic forces and does not directly indicate if a structure will buckle or not. Each element has three values of $\lambda_{cr,ref}$ representing the longitudinal, transverse and shear loading.

2.5 Optimised stacking sequence selection

For each GSST case the minimum values of $\lambda_{cr,ref}$ (three values) are compared to determine the optimum case of stacking sequences. The comparison of the three $\lambda_{cr,ref}$ values per case is performed via a pareto surface and the case which has the minimum distance from the origin on the pareto surface is chosen as the optimum stacking sequence. The optimum stacking sequences for each zone as well as the global ply continuity, design rules compliance, manufacturing rules compliance and total mass are exported to file on completion. The global ply continuity is re-computed after the final stacking sequences are chosen. This is done by calculating the ratio between the total number of plies which can be laid across the entire structure and the number of plies in the thickest laminate.

The optimum stacking sequences and material properties are then used to generate the NASTRAN GFEM input files.

3 Global finite element analysis

The NASTRAN FE code is used to perform a linear elastic analysis on the structure to predict failure in the laminates. Only a section of the aircraft around the PAX door was analysed as can be seen in Fig. 2 but the full aircraft structure and loading was accounted for in the FE model via super elements in NASTRAN (FE model provided by Bombardier Aerospace, Montreal). The model provided by Bombardier was the baseline metallic structure which was converted for composite structure analysis. Additionally, the structure was subdivided into domains which were suitable for an optimisation study. The updated division of zones can be seen in Fig. 5. The material properties for the finite element model were provided by Bombardier and design reserve factors were directly factored into the material properties.

The model has 77 load cases for which a first ply failure analysis is performed using the maximum strain failure criterion. The generation and post-

processing of the finite element analysis is automated using PYTHON scripting. The output from the model is the total mass of the structure and the maximum strain failure indices. The post-processing script then computes the real buckling factors (where λ_{cr} values less than 1 represent buckling of the structure) based on the element forces from the finite element model.

4 Global optimisation methodology

The purpose of the optimisation was to minimise the mass of the composite skins on the surround structure of the passenger door while:

- Ensuring that the structure does not fail
- Ensuring that the structure does not buckle
- Ensuring that the manufacturing constraints are respected
- Ensuring that the design constraints are respected
- Obtaining maximum possible global ply continuity

The previous sections of this paper discuss how all of these factors can be assessed.

Minamo offers the user the capability to perform single and multi-objective optimisations by means of generating a constantly evolving surrogate model representing the behaviour of the structure. It also offers the ability to use integer and discrete variable parameters for its genetic algorithms [9].

For this study a surrogate based single objective optimisation was used with multiple constraints and discrete integer parameters. The objective and constraints were normalised to ensure equal weighting.

In this benchmark study, there are 5 contributing factors to the fitness function of the individual. The first is the mass which needs to be minimised (objective). Next we have the failure index computed in the finite element analysis which needs to be kept below 1 (constraint 1). We then have the critical buckling factor which needs to be greater than or equal to 1 (constraint 2). Finally we have the manufacturability (constraint 3) and the global ply continuity (constraint 4) which need to be above a certain percentage (user defined). The objectives, constraints and parameters (design variables) are summarised in Table 3.

To reduce the number of failed cases, a co-dependence of parameters was introduced. This

prevents situations where the difference in total number of plies for neighbouring zones is more than 4. This step is performed before entering the local optimisation as a temporary measure. In a future version of this optimisation chain this inter-parameter dependency will be handled directly by Minamo.

6 Results and discussions

The optimisation was setup as discussed in the previous sections and the initial parameters used have been listed in Table 4.

The optimisation was run on Cenaero's cluster using 16 GB of ram and 10 processors. A design of experiment (DoE) size of 75 experiments was chosen to build the meta-model and 200 generations of the genetic algorithm were run.

Before running the genetic algorithm the quality of the meta-model was verified using a correlation analysis (Leave One Out (LOO) analysis). The LOO analysis checks the quality of the meta-model by comparing the analytically computed fitness function against the numerically computed fitness function. The result from this analysis for each of the contributing factors to the fitness function can be seen in Fig. 6.

It can be seen that the LOO analysis shows that the meta-model shows good correlation to the numerical computation (all values are above 80%).

On completion of the full optimisation, the convergence of the primary objective (Mass) was analysed and has been plotted in Fig. 7. The results in the convergence plot include all iterations which did not receive a failed status from the local optimisation (even individuals which will structurally fail and fail in buckling). We see that during the DoE the whole solution space is tested and during the optimisation, the optimum configuration is reached almost immediately. This shows that 200 generations of the genetic algorithm were not required to achieve the optimum.

A summary of the optimum results are listed in Table 5 to Table 8. The optimum solution was found to have a mass reduction (skin) of 21% (with respect to the baseline metallic skin) with a global manufacturability of 100 % and a global ply continuity of 87.5 % (all optimisation constraints were satisfied).

7 Conclusions and further work

A novel methodology to optimise large composite structures efficiently while respecting design and manufacturing rules was presented. A mixed analytical and numerical methodology was adopted in order to reduce the normally large design space associated with tailoring stacking sequences in real-life structures. The optimum stacking sequences chosen by optimisation proved the ability of the tool to successfully identify reduced mass structures with high compliance to design and manufacturing rules. The methodology presented is a proof-of-concept which requires further development to increase robustness and functionality. Some of the primary areas of improvement and potential limitations have been listed below:

- More efficient construction of the global stacking sequence table (GSST) by performing the design rules assessment and elimination of non-feasible results before the construction of the GSST
- Accommodation of neutral mid-plane plies
- The ability to use different materials within a stacking sequence (hybrid laminates)
- Intrinsic testing on the effect of changing load-paths due to changing stacking sequences on the global level optimisation
- Sensitivity analysis on the effect of weighting of constraints and objectives
- Implementation of transverse shear effects into buckling computation

Figures and tables

Fig. 1. Illustration of the optimisation chain

Fig. 2. GFEM of fuselage section provided by Bombardier

Fig. 3. Illustration of stacking sequence generation tool

Fig. 4. Illustration of loading types for buckling

Fig. 5. Domain definition for the finite element model

Fig. 6. LOO analysis – Correlation coefficients

Fig. 7. Convergence of Mass objective

Structural Design Rules	
Rule 1	Symmetric
Rule 2	Balanced
Rule 3	10% of each orientation
Rule 4	Max. 3 plies of same orientation grouped
Rule 5	$\pm 45^\circ$ plies have max. 1 ply between them
Rule 6	Max. 45° angle between ply and a group of more than 1 plies with the same orientation
Rule 7	Outer plies should be $\pm 45^\circ$
Manufacturing Rules	
Rule 8	Max. Poisson's ratio mismatch 0.15
Rule 9	Outer plies continuous
Rule 10	Max. ply drops = 4
Rule 11	Drop $\pm 45^\circ$ plies together
Rule 12	Drop inner plies first

Table 1. Rules for design and manufacture of composite structures

Stage	P1	P2	P3	P4
Initial	(3,2,2)	(3,3,2)	(2,4,1)	(4,2,1)
Shared Layer 1	(2,2,1)	(2,2,1)	(2,2,1)	(2,2,1)
Remaining (Intermediate)	(1,0,1)	(1,1,1)	(0,2,0)	(2,0,0)
Shared Layer 2	(1,0,1)	(1,0,1)	(0,0,0)	(1,0,0)
Remaining (Final)	(0,0,0)	(0,1,0)	(0,2,0)	(1,0,0)

Table 2. Four domain example of shared layer blending

Objectives	Constraints	Parameters
Min. Mass	Failure index < 1 $\lambda_{cr} \geq 1$ Manufacturability > 0.9 Global ply continuity > 0.7	No. of plies per laminate

Table 3. Summary of optimisation objectives, constraints and parameters

Parameters			
Variable		Constant	
Domain	No. Plies	Rule	Compliance
1205040	16	Rule 1	100%
1205050	16	Rule 2	100%
1205058	16	Rule 3	100%
1205060	16	Rule 4	100%
1205100	16	Rule 5	100%
2000041	16	Rule 6	50%
2000050	16	Rule 7	100%
2000060	16	Rule 8	100%
1205103	16	Rule 9	100%
1205101	16	Rule 10	100%
1205102	16	Rule 11	100%
1205045	16	Rule 12	100%
Maximum Ply Drops			4
Global Ply Continuity			70%
Manufacturability			90%

Table 4. Optimisation initial parameters

Zone	Stacking Sequence
1205040	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$
1205050	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$
1205058	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$
1205060	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$
1205100	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$
2000041	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$
2000050	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$
2000060	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$
1205103	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_s$
1205101	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$
1205102	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$
1205045	$[-45^\circ/45^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$

Table 5. Summary of optimum results: Stacking sequences

Zone	Compliance of design rules						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1205040	100	100	100	100	100	95.71	100
1205050	100	100	100	100	100	95.71	100
1205058	100	100	100	100	100	94.64	100
1205060	100	100	100	100	100	95.71	100
1205100	100	100	100	100	100	96.43	100
2000041	100	100	100	100	100	95.71	100
2000050	100	100	100	100	100	95.71	100
2000060	100	100	100	100	100	94.64	100
1205103	100	100	100	100	100	96.43	100
1205101	100	100	100	100	100	96.94	100
1205102	100	100	100	100	100	96.94	100
1205045	100	100	100	100	100	95.71	100

Table 6. Summary of optimum results: Compliance of design rules

Zone 1	Zone 2	Compliance of manufacturing rules				
		8	9	10	11	12
1205058	1205040	100	100	100	100	100
1205060	1205102	100	100	100	100	100
1205060	1205040	100	100	100	100	100
1205060	1205045	100	100	100	100	100
1205045	1205102	100	100	100	100	100
1205045	1205040	100	100	100	100	100
1205045	1205050	100	100	100	100	100
1205050	1205103	100	100	100	100	100
1205050	1205101	100	100	100	100	100
1205050	1205040	100	100	100	100	100
1205050	1205102	100	100	100	100	100
1205040	2000050	100	100	100	100	100
1205040	2000041	100	100	100	100	100
1205040	1205100	100	100	100	100	100
1205040	2000060	100	100	100	100	100
2000041	2000050	100	100	100	100	100
2000060	2000050	100	100	100	100	100
1205102	1205101	100	100	100	100	100
1205102	1205100	100	100	100	100	100
1205103	1205101	100	100	100	100	100
Global Manufacturability		100 %				
Global Ply Continuity		87.5%				

Table 7. Summary of optimum results: Compliance of manufacturing rules

Primary Objectives	Result	Desired result/Reference
Critical buckling factor	1.28	> 1.0
Critical failure index	0.74	< 1.0
Skin mass reduction	21 %	Metallic skin

Table 8. Summary of optimum results: Primary objectives

References

- [1] ‘*Polymer Matrix Composites*’, MIL-HDBK-17 (4th edn.), vol. 1 Guidelines, Dept. of Defense Washington DC, 1994
- [2] D. Quinn, A. Murphy, M.A. Price and M. Mullan, ‘Impact of composite manufacturing constraints on aerospace stiffened panel design’, *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Composite Materials*, ICC Jeju, Korea, Applications of composites, M04-5, August 21-26 2011
- [3] O. Seresta, Z. Gurdal, D.B. Adams, L.T. Watson, ‘Optimal design of composite wing structures with blended laminates’, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, Volume 38, Issue 4, June 2007, Pages 469-480
- [4] D. Liu, V.V. Toropov, D.C. Barton, O.M. Querin, ‘Bilevel optimisation of blended composite wing

panels’, *Journal of aircraft*, Vol. 48, No. 01, Jan-Feb 2011

- [5] G. van Rossum and F.L. Drake, ‘*Python Reference Manual*’. PythonLabs, Virginia, USA, 2001. Available at <http://www.python.org>
- [6] V.L. Lemos, S.G. Castro and J.A. Hernandes, ‘Integrating automatic zone modelling with GA in a two-step approach for structural optimization of a composite wing’, *Proceedings of the 3rd International conference on engineering optimization*, Rio de Janeiro, July 01-05 2012
- [7] L.P. Kollar and G.S. Springer, ‘*Mechanics of composite structures*’. Illustrated reprint edition, Cambridge University Press, 2003.
- [8] C. Kassapoglou, ‘Design and analysis of composite structures: with applications to aerospace structures’. Illustrated edition, Wiley, 2010.
- [9] C. Sainvitu, V. Ilipoulou and I. Lepot ‘Global optimization with expensive functions – sample turbomachinery design application’. *Springer*, Vol. Recent advances in optimisation and its applications in engineering, pp 499-509, 2010.